

Studies on polyvalent metal ion bound polyacrylate

Aloke Chattopadhyay

Department of Chemistry, S. B. College, Bagati, Mogra, Hooghly-712 148, West Bengal, India

E-mail : aloke.chattopadhyay09@gmail.com

Manuscript received online 19 January 2013, revised 26 February 2013, accepted 01 March 2013

Abstract : Preparation of $Y_1Ba_2Cu_{2.84}O_{6.58}$ (superconducting material) from polymeric precursor technique using sodium polyacrylate as the polymeric part has been already reported. But the material may contain BaO impurity. This BaO probably forms because of formation of $Ba(OH)_2$ byproduct if excess amount of $Ba(NO_3)_2$ solution is added during formation of polyvalent metal ion bound polymeric part. SEM and EDS studies indicate the presence of barium compounds as undesired byproduct in the sample. To avoid this undesired $Ba(OH)_2$ formation, amount of $Ba(NO_3)_2$ solution addition is to be adjusted. When 9 ml $Ba(NO_3)_2$ solution is added instead of 17.5 ml in this experiment, to prepare polyvalent metal ion bound macromolecular part, it has been found that peak at 855.76 cm^{-1} in IR spectra, which is attributed to undesired $Ba(OH)_2$, is minimized. So 9 ml $Ba(NO_3)_2$ solution may be the better choice.

Keywords : Ceramic oxide, polymeric precursor, barium hydroxide, spectroscopy.

Introduction

Yttrium barium copper oxide can be prepared by polymeric precursor technique^{1,2}. It has been found that aqueous solution of guar gum-graft-acrylamide binds Y^{3+} at pH near about 9.5, Ba^{2+} at pH near about 12.5 and Cu^{2+} at pH near about 6³. In this case, $-COO^-$ group from guar gum-graft-acrylamide, mainly takes part in binding polyvalent metal ion when pH is raised^{4,5}. So sodium polyacrylate may be the better choice to bind polyvalent metal ion. When sodium polyacrylate has been used to prepare yttrium barium copper oxide, it has been found that barium oxide may form as impurity^{1,2}. This undesired BaO formation is probably due to formation of $Ba(OH)_2$ for excess addition of $Ba(NO_3)_2$ solution during mixing of polymer solution, $Y(NO_3)_3$ solution, $Ba(NO_3)_2$ solution, $Cu(NO_3)_2$ solution and 60% NaOH solution. In this present investigation 25 ml approximately 3.2% sodium polyacrylate solution is mixed with 17.5 ml $Ba(NO_3)_2$ solution and specified amounts of $Y(NO_3)_3$ solution, $Cu(NO_3)_2$ solution and 60% NaOH solution to get a sample. Similarly another sample is obtained by mixing 13 ml $Ba(NO_3)_2$ solution along with others and another sample is prepared by using 9 ml $Ba(NO_3)_2$ solution along with others. When 9 ml $Ba(NO_3)_2$ solution has been added, it has been found that $Ba(OH)_2$ formation is minimized. So 9 ml $Ba(NO_3)_2$ solution may be the right choice.

Materials and methods :

(i) Metal nitrate solutions :

$Y(NO_3)_3$ solution or $Cu(NO_3)_2$ solution is prepared by dissolving Y_2O_3 or CuO in nitric acid to get approximately 0.2 (M) solution. $Ba(NO_3)_2$ solution has been prepared by dissolving $Ba(NO_3)_2$ in distilled water to get approximately 0.1 (M) solution.

(ii) Sodium polyacrylate :

Polyacrylic acid 2100 sodium salt (Fluka) (from Sigma Aldrich) has been used in this work. The material is soluble in water.

(iii) Preparation of samples :

25 ml approximately 3.2% sodium polyacrylate solution is mixed with 5 ml $Y(NO_3)_3$ solution, 17.5 ml $Ba(NO_3)_2$ solution and 12.5 ml $Cu(NO_3)_2$ solution and pH of the mixture is raised by adding 10 ml approximately 60% NaOH solution. A bluish precipitate is obtained. 50 ml methanol is added and allowed the mixture to stand for overnight. Liquid is decanted off and again washed with methyl alcohol for several times by decantation and then is dried in an oven to get sample 1 for SEM, EDS and IR spectral studies. Sample 2, sample 3 and sample 4 have been prepared as shown in Table 1.

(iv) Preparation of barium hydroxide :

10 ml $Ba(NO_3)_2$ solution is mixed with 10 ml 60% NaOH to get a white precipitate. It is allowed to stand for overnight

Table 1

Sample	Volume of approx. 3.2% sodium polyacrylate solution used (ml)	Volume of $Y(NO_3)_3$ solution mixed (ml)	Volume of $Ba(NO_3)_2$ solution mixed (ml)	Volume of $Cu(NO_3)_2$ solution mixed (ml)	Volume of 60% NaOH solution mixed (ml)	Washing with methanol for several times	Dried for IR spectral study and SEM
Sample 1	25	5	17.5	12.5	10	By decantation	Without filtration
Sample 2	25	5	17.5	12.5	10	By decantation	After filtration
Sample 3	25	5	13	12.5	10	By decantation	After filtration
Sample 4	25	5	9	12.5	10	By decantation	After filtration

and then filtered and washed with distilled water for several times. It is dried in an oven for IR spectral study.

(v) *IR spectral study* :

IR spectra for sodium polyacrylate, barium hydroxide and for sample 1 to sample 4 are recorded with Perkin-Elmer Spectrum 100 FTIR spectrometer using KBr pallet.

(vi) *SEM and EDS* :

Scanning Electron Microscopic (SEM) experiment and Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS) for sample 1 have been carried out using SCANNING MICROSCOPE (JEOL company made in Japan) model number JSM5800. For SEM, gold coated sample has been used. Gold coating has been done by SPUTTERING TECHNIQUE. For EDS, sample is not gold coated. EDS study has been carried out using Oxford Instruments (INCA Software).

Results and discussion

(i) *SEM and EDS* :

SEM image (Fig. 1) indicates presence of various phases. It contains small white particles, big white particles, rod-like phase, grey agglomerates etc.

Fig. 1. SEM image for sample 1.

Bulk EDS study indicates the presence of the following atoms in the sample (sample 1) as shown in Table 2.

Table 2

Element	Weight (%)	Atomic (%)
C K	16.53	28.09
O K	37.24	47.50
Na K	21.07	18.70
Cu K	7.96	2.56
Y L	7.31	1.68
Ba L	9.88	1.47
Total	100.00	

Hydrogen can not be detected in this process.

EDS study indicates small white particle (spectrum 2 of Fig. 2) is barium hydroxide (Fig. 3) (Table 3).

Fig. 2. Small white particle for EDS.

Fig. 3. Analysis for small white particle (spectrum 2 of Fig. 2) by EDS.

Table 3

Element	Weight (%)	Atomic (%)
C K	14.78	29.58
O K	28.32	42.57
Na K	20.17	21.10
Cu K	1.57	0.59
Ba L	35.16	6.16
Total	100.00	

EDS study indicates white particles (spectrum 3 of Fig. 4) are rich in copper content (Fig. 5) (Table 4).

Big white particle (spectrum 3 of Fig. 6) contains C, O, Y, Ba, Cu and Na (Fig. 7) (Table 5).

Rod like phase (spectrum 2 of Fig. 8) indicates NaOH (Fig. 9) (Table 6).

Fig. 4. White particle for EDS.

Fig. 5. Analysis for white particle (spectrum 3 of Fig. 4) by EDS.

Table 4

Element	Weight (%)	Atomic (%)
C K	11.89	25.46
O K	23.07	37.10
Na K	16.48	18.44
Cu K	45.52	18.43
Ba L	3.04	0.57
Total	100.00	

Fig. 6. Big white particle for EDS.

Grey agglomerate (spectrum 3 of Fig. 10) contains C, O, Y, Ba, Cu and Na (Fig. 11) (Table 7).

(ii) IR spectral study :

In IR spectra for sodium polyacrylate (Fig. 12), peaks at 1570.70 cm^{-1} and 1408.54 cm^{-1} can be attributed to COO^- asymmetric stretch ($\nu_{\text{as.CO}^-}$) and COO^- symmet-

Fig. 7. Analysis for big white particle (spectrum 3 of Fig. 6) by EDS.

Table 5

Element	Weight (%)	Atomic (%)
C K	14.70	26.59
O K	34.61	47.01
Na K	17.04	16.11
Cu K	24.46	8.36
Y L	5.48	1.34
Ba L	3.72	0.59
Total	100.00	

Fig. 8. Rod like phase for EDS.

ric stretch (ν_{s,COO^-}) respectively. In IR spectra for barium hydroxide (Fig. 13), peak at 855.76 cm^{-1} can be attributed to M-O-H bending vibration.

In IR spectra for sample 1 (Fig. 14), peak at 1565.94

Fig. 9. Analysis for rod like phase (spectrum 2 of Fig. 8) by EDS.

Table 6

Element	Weight (%)	Atomic (%)
C K	16.33	26.44
O K	33.13	40.28
Na K	35.40	29.95
Cu K	7.23	2.21
Ba L	7.91	1.12
Total	100.00	

Fig. 10. Grey agglomerate for EDS.

cm^{-1} can be attributed COO^- asymmetric stretch and peak at 1384.42 cm^{-1} can be attributed to COO^- symmetric stretch. Different positions of these peaks from those of Fig. 12 for sodium polyacrylate indicate binding of polyvalent metal ion by polyacrylate. EDS study indicates sample 1 contains undesired NaOH and $Ba(OH)_2$.

Fig. 11. Analysis for grey agglomerate (spectrum 3 of Fig. 10) by EDS.

Table 7

Element	Weight (%)	Atomic (%)
C K	20.01	36.33
O K	30.19	41.15
Na K	15.86	15.05
Cu K	3.49	1.20
Y L	16.59	4.07
Ba L	13.87	2.20
Total	100.00	

Fig. 12. IR spectra for sodium polyacrylate.

IR spectra for sample 1 indicates multiple peaks (Fig. 14 and Fig. 15) near about at 857.65 cm^{-1} which can be attributed to NaOH, $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ etc. To minimize NaOH content, filtration has been done before drying in case of sample 2, sample 3 and sample 4. Surprisingly it has been found that multiple peaks near about at 857.65 cm^{-1} in the IR spectra for sample 2 (Fig. 16) is absent. Peak at

Fig. 13. IR spectra for barium hydroxide.

Fig. 14. IR spectra for sample 1.

Fig. 15. IR spectra for sample 1 (broad view).

856.07 cm^{-1} in the IR spectra for sample 2 can be attributed to bending vibration for $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ phase. So IR spec-

Fig. 16. IR spectra for sample 2.

tral studies suggest that filtration may minimize NaOH phase.

Another major problem for preparation of yttrium barium copper oxide by polymeric precursor technique using sodium polyacrylate is the presence of undesired BaO phase^{1,2}. Formation of undesired BaO may occur from undesired Ba(OH)₂ phase. Formation of undesired Ba(OH)₂ can be avoided by proper control of amount of Ba(NO₃)₂ solution added during preparation of polyvalent metal ion bound polyacrylate. In case of sample 2, 17.5 ml Ba(NO₃)₂ solution has been added and IR spectra for sample 2 (Fig. 16) indicates sharp peak at 856.07 cm⁻¹ which can be attributed to Ba(OH)₂ phase. Relative intensity of this corresponding peak has been considerably reduced (Fig. 17) when 13 ml Ba(NO₃)₂ solution has

Fig. 17. IR spectra for sample 3.

been added to prepare sample 3. When 9 ml Ba(NO₃)₂ solution has been added to prepare sample 4, relative intensity of this corresponding peak (Fig. 18) has been minimized. So 9 ml Ba(NO₃)₂ solution may be the desired amount.

Fig. 18. IR spectra for sample 4.

Conclusion

Preparation of yttrium barium copper oxide by polymeric precursor technique is important in Materials Science. This work may help in preparation of yttrium barium copper oxide without producing undesired barium oxide impurity using sodium polyacrylate as the polymer. So this approach may open a new area in the preparation of useful ceramic oxide.

Acknowledgement

Author acknowledges thanks to Dr. N. R. Jana *et al.* of IACS, Kolkata for their help and co-operation to carry out this work. Author also acknowledges thanks to Sikharesh Mallick, Ex-student of S. B. College, Bagati, Mogra, Hooghly, West Bengal, India for his help.

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